

THE URGENCY OF FIRST AID TRAINING IN ISLAMIC BOARDINGS SCHOOLS AZ-ZABUR PEKALONGAN

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Abstract

Basically, knowledge and understanding of first aid is very important for the community. Where first aid is the first step that medical lay people can take to provide assistance to others who are in need of quick and immediate help. Seeing the importance of first aid knowledge, UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Istitute of Pekalongan Unit held a training entitled The Urgency of First Aid Training at the Az-Zabur Islamic Boarding School Pekalongan. This training uses several methods, such as lecture, practice, and discussion methods. Lectures are used to open the material. While the practical method is used in the delivery of aid procedures, how to help and the use of first aid support tools. The data analysis technique in this first aid journal uses qualitative data analysis techniques, where the data obtained is not in the form of numbers. The research is based on Usman's theory, that first aid is the provision of immediate assistance to sick people or accident victims who require basic medical treatment to prevent disability or death. The results of this training show that education and assistance to all levels of society is really needed, especially the students at the Az-Zabur Islamic Boarding School regarding first aid training. With the aim, so that students have adequate skills and knowledge about first aid. So that they are able to provide independent treatment if there is a medical case that makes them have to help others.

Keywords: First aid, pesantren, urgency, and education.

Introduction

Accidents or medical emergencies can happen anywhere and regardless of place (Roy et al., 2020). One of the places that has a lot of potential for medical emergencies is a boarding school. In Indonesia, especially in Pekalongan itself, there are still many Islamic boarding schools that do not yet have supporting medical or health facilities. Therefore, teaching first aid knowledge is important (Workneh et al., 2021). Noting that Islamic boarding schools are places that accommodate many people, thereby increasing the potential for medical emergencies to occur. If this great potential is not balanced with good medical facilities, it can result in assistance or the provision of care for students who are sick and require immediate medical assistance, not receiving proper and good attention and treatment (Ssewante et al., 2022). So to overcome the lack of medical facilities, it is necessary to teach knowledge about first aid to students. It is hoped that the students will have good provisions in the event of a medical emergency and are able to provide assistance according to the guidelines and can support the healing process of the patient. In addition, in order to provide a good understanding of the relief process (Alsufyani et al., 2022). Because if the first aid is carried out inappropriately, it can result in the patient's injury getting worse and worsening the patient's condition. Many people are not aware that in fact the wrong handling of first aid can be fatal (Husna and Agustin, 2018, p. 136). Not infrequently handling accidents in patients actually worsens his condition. Spinal injuries can even result in spinal or cervical fractures, sprains, or even additional bleeding that can occur if the treatment given is not

appropriate or even wrong (Alkhotani, 2022). Seeing the importance of first aid knowledge (Banstola et al., 2021), UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit held a first aid training activity with the main target being students in Islamic boarding schools. With the intention that the students have adequate skills and knowledge about first aid. So that they are able to provide independent treatment if there are medical cases that make them have to help others. So that it can slightly overcome the problem of lack of adequate health facilities.

In this training UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit delivered first aid based on medical cases commonly encountered in the community, such as fainting, asthma, fever, and bleeding. With the presenters taken from internal based on the discussion of PP material. The main purpose of this activity is to share knowledge about first aid to the students. Because in UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit itself there are trainings and practices related to First Aid and those related to the material so that it makes us more confident to share this knowledge about first aid with others. In addition, this training activity is a form of dedication of UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit to the community about teaching in the basic medical field. Because the purpose of students is to be the main actors and agents of exchange in an effort to have meaning in human intellectual life who views everything with students' minds, they are a group of young people who have a strategic role because students are a source of moral strength (moral force) for the Indonesian nation (Kosasih, 2016). p.65). This is a form of dedication from UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit as a form of change to the community directly in the field of basic medical treatment.

The research that is relevant to this activity is the research conducted by Anggraini, et al (2018) which raised the title of First Aid Health Education in Accidents in the Community in Dandangan Village. In the research conducted, it describes techniques in performing first aid in a concise and easy to understand manner. The object of research or training activities is the Dandangan Village community (Shafi et al., 2022). However, the research conducted does not explain in detail the details of the activities carried out, does not include details of the intent, purpose, and delivery method so that the reader does not understand how the teaching techniques are carried out in the study (Shan et al., 2022). The research is relevant to the activities carried out by UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit because it raises the topic of teaching first aid knowledge to the community (Crooks et al., 2018). The location of the difference in activities is found in the object of research (Cheng et al., 2021). In research conducted by Anggraini, the object of activity is directly to the people of the Dandangan village. While the objects in the training activities carried out by UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit specifically were students from the Az-Zabur Pekalongan Islamic boarding school. With a clear and specific object of activity, they will be better able to prepare material that is more relevant and needed directly by Islamic boarding school students, thus the benefits obtained will be higher than teaching activities that are not specific to the object or target. In addition, the maturity of the material and the teaching provided can be prepared better and neater (Abelairas-Gómez et al., 2020).

The next research is a research conducted by Muhammad and Nugroho (2019) with the title Design of First Aid Needs on Preparedness for Handling Daily Accidents for Elementary School Children. In this study, the activities carried out were collecting data and classifying cases that were often found in elementary schools. From the data found, it was then disseminated to staff and teachers who worked in the schools under study. In this study, data collection was conducted on 3 elementary schools in Ternate. In this study, the researcher presented the data obtained in detail and then described the data presented as well as solving problems from the data presented. The data taken and presented are data on common medical cases and are commonly found in elementary schools. And the elaboration carried out is a description of the handling of cases obtained from the data obtained. However, the research conducted there are shortcomings in the socialization and implementation of training for employees and teachers who work in these elementary schools. Thus the reader is less able to understand how to follow up on the data obtained. In the activities carried out by UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit, there are similarities and relevance in handling the same case. The cases encountered in the research carried out were relatively the same as the teaching carried out by UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit at the Az-Zabur Islamic boarding school. However, the research

conducted by Muhammad and Nugroho is not very clear in describing the direction given to teachers or staff working in these elementary schools.

The results and discussion section will discuss why the activities carried out are considered urgent and need to be carried out. In addition, the material presented in the teaching activities will also be discussed. Follow-up or the results obtained will also be conveyed concisely and clearly.

Methods

The methods used in this training activity are lecture, practice, and discussion methods (Kaur et al., 2019). Training is part of education regarding the learning process to acquire and improve skills outside the applicable education system, in a relatively short time and with methods that prioritize practice over theory (Rohmah, 2018, p. 3). Lectures are used to open the material, delivered by a presenter who will guide the course of the training. Lectures are the first part to start practice. By using the lecture method, it is hoped that participants will be able to recognize and capture the material that will be delivered in the training (Sun et al., 2020). The lecture method is quite suitable for the audience of Islamic boarding school students who are actually equal to the high school level and some students at the student level. The lecture method is an important part in developing the public speaking skills of members of UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit. Good speaking abilities and skills can be possessed by honing and cultivating and training all existing potential (Fitrandi, 2018, p. 67).

The next method used is the practical method (Cohen et al., 2022). This method is used in delivering first aid procedures, how to help and the use of first aid support tools. The practical method is used because the main focus of the activities carried out is training the skills and abilities of the participants. So that the practice method is in accordance with the expected focus of activities. Training participants will be more familiar with the material presented if the method used can be directly demonstrated and carefully exemplified. The next method used is the discussion method. Discussion is used as a medium for participants to ask about things they do not know. This discussion method is carried out after carrying out the practice. This is done so that the training participants can ask questions related to things they do not understand when doing the practice. Opening the minds of participants and making training activities not only run in one direction but can run in two directions because there is a response from the training participants. The discussion is also part of the review of the material presented.

In practice, the First Aid Training activities are held at the Az-Zabur Islamic Boarding School Pekalongan, which is located at Jl. Diponegoro, Sidokerti, Kajen, Kajen District, Pekalongan. Held on Sunday, April 25, 2021. 08.00-12.00 WIB. Because it coincided with the new normal period, the activities were carried out by implementing health protocols. Such as using masks, using hand sanitizers, and checking body temperature before participants and committees enter the training venue. Limiting the number of people in one room by taking into account the number of people and the size of the room. Stick to the 50% room usage regulation with a maximum number of 30 people in one room. In the implementation using a wide hall, 50% of the room can be used to accommodate 25 participants and several committee members.

Result and Discussion

Based on the First Aid Training activities conducted, it showed that the participants were interested in the topics discussed in the training. Referring to the discussion section which states that there are many Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia, especially in Pekalongan, which do not have access to adequate medical services, it can be proven by the responses from participants who expressed their opinions regarding the governance of the health services that their cottages provide. In addition, during the training, it can also be noted that the participants of the activity seemed unfamiliar with the material presented by the presenters related to the material of medical cases that are commonly encountered on a daily basis. This is evidenced by their low understanding of how to handle the submitted medical cases. Therefore, from these findings it can be answered why this training is urgently carried out with an audience of Islamic boarding school students.

If you judge how important first aid knowledge is to Islamic boarding school students, the answer is very important. In the life of the boarding school the students are used to doing everything independently.

Therefore, the provision of first aid teaching is considered to have a good effect, namely they are able to apply it to the environment and most importantly are able to apply it to themselves in case of a medical emergency.

Materials delivered in the training included materials on handling fainting, fever, and asthma or shortness of breath. The following is a description of the material presented in the training carried out.

Handling of Fainting

Fainting occurs because blood circulation to the brain is reduced, which can occur due to intense emotions, being in a room full of people without enough fresh air, tired and hungry, expending too much energy (Usman, 2008, p. 99). Symptoms that occur if you are about to pass out are feeling unsteady, dizzy vision and ringing in the ears, weakness, cold sweats, yawning, can be unresponsive which usually lasts only a few minutes, characterized by slow and weak pulse.

Handling that can be done is in the first way, namely laying the patient with the feet higher than the heart, it can be done by placing the patient's feet in the lap of the rescuer or propping him up with objects that are not hard and contain such as bags or pillows, the feet are higher than the heart has the aim of normalizing blood circulation to the head. Then loosen the patient's clothing such as belts, watches, ties, collars, and headscarves.

After that, try to get the patient in a place that has good air circulation by keeping it away from the crowd or taking him shelter. After the patient's condition is safe and comfortable, it is necessary to check whether there are other injuries such as bleeding or sprains by paying attention to every part of the patient's body. Give a blanket to the patient to feel warm and comfortable, do not give perfume or the like because it is not effective and there are some patients who may have allergies to fragrances that can cause shortness of breath. If the patient is conscious, rest for 5-10 minutes until the dizziness and lightheadedness disappear. And if more than 15-20 minutes has not shown a response, then immediately refer to the nearest health facility.

Penanganan pada Demam

Fever is a condition where the body temperature is higher than usual, and is a symptom of an illness. Human body temperature can be said to be fever if it exceeds 37 degrees Celsius. Fever is the body's normal response to infection. Infection is the entry of microorganisms into the body, which can be in the form of viruses, bacteria, parasites, or fungi

Actions and anticipations that can be done to provide help to people with fever are first to give paracetamol in the form of syrup or tablets according to the rules, and if the temperature is more than 40°C, do compresses with warm water, give lots of drinks, next is to keep the patient in a room where warm with a constant temperature, with adequate ventilation, not windows that have airflow (Usman, 2008, pp. 128-129). Handling of fever or first aid that can be done to reduce body temperature when fever can be done physically (non-pharmacologically) by using heat energy through conduction and evaporation methods. The conduction method is the transfer of heat from an object to another by direct contact. When warm skin touches a warm one, there will be heat transfer through evaporation, so that the transfer of heat energy turns into gas. An example of conduction and evaporation methods is the use of warm compresses. (Cahyaningrum, 2017, p.67).

Asthma Treatment

Asthma is a chronic inflammatory disorder of the airways that involves many cells and elements. Continuous inflammation causes increased hyperresponsiveness in the airways resulting in recurrent episodic symptoms in the form of shortness of breath, chest tightness, wheezing, and especially at night and or during the day (Rahmah, 2020, p. 147). Asthma can occur due to several factors such as the presence of a virus, or due to allergies, even due to the presence of irritants or materials that can cause irritation to the body, especially in breathing (PDPI, 2004, p. 35).

Handling that can be done if you encounter a case of asthma is as follows, first position the patient in a sitting position with his back fully leaning on a chair or wall. In addition to using a wall or chair, you can use the shin of the helper's leg as a place to lean on the patient. Try not to bend over and remain seated in a comfortable position. After that, give breathing instructions to the patient. When there is asthma, most

sufferers will experience panic and it will be difficult to control their own breathing. Therefore, providing assistance with breathing instructions is very important. Do not let the crowd around the patient so as not to block air circulation.

When doing help for asthma, most sufferers will experience panic and cry. In order for the help to be effective, it is necessary to calm the patient so that he stops crying and does not panic. Give an inhaler, oxygen or asthma spray to provide comfort when the sufferer breathes. If the patient's breathing gets heavier after 10-15 minutes, then immediately refer to the nearest health facility.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the first aid training carried out by UKK KSR PMI of State Islamic Institute of Pekalongan Unit to students at the Az-Zabur Islamic Boarding School Pekalongan, it can be concluded that education and assistance to all levels of society, especially the students at the Az-Zabur Islamic Boarding School is very much needed. zabur regarding first aid training. With the aim, so that students have adequate skills and knowledge about first aid. So that they are able to provide independent treatment if there is a medical case that makes them have to help others.

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